

<p>Guía (substitution; MAJOR) launches (unidiomatic style; MINOR) (grammar; MINOR) new subscription program Flex guide (substitution; MAJOR), where you can rent your car from (grammar; NEUTRAL) 6 (inconsistent with external reference; NEUTRAL) months (awkward style; NEUTRAL) to 24 months, either (grammar; MINOR) electric or combustion. 1 (substitution; MINOR) 100x100 (substitution; MINOR) digital process where you can see if (grammar; NEUTRAL) you are automatically approved to take (grammar; NEUTRAL) this (grammar; MINOR) car or not (grammar; NEUTRAL) (punctuation; MINOR) and you will be able to dispose of it (mistranslation; MINOR) within 1 (substitution; MINOR) period of time (unidiomatic style; MINOR) (grammar; MINOR) 1 (substitution; NEUTRAL) to 2 (substitution; NEUTRAL) weeks at the latest. Including (substitution; MINOR) what? Well, including (substitution; MINOR) all (punctuation; MINOR) maintenance (capitalisation; MINOR), breakdowns, roadside assistance (textual conventions; MINOR). With this program (punctuation; NEUTRAL) we are (language register; NEUTRAL) running out of excuses in order to not have (mistranslation; MINOR) 1 (substitution; MINOR) vehicle Kia (grammar; MINOR) and these new Kia (addition; NEUTRAL) mobility services (punctuation; MINOR) (deletion; MINOR)</p>	<p>substitution; MAJOR</p>		
		substitution; MAJOR	2
	unidiomatic style; MINOR	unidiomatic style; MINOR	2
	grammar; MINOR	grammar; MINOR	5
	substitution; MAJOR	grammar; NEUTRAL	4
	grammar; NEUTRAL	inconsistent with external referenc	1
	inconsistent with external reference; NEUTRAL	awkward style; NEUTRAL	1
	awkward style; NEUTRAL	substitution; MINOR	6
	grammar; MINOR	punctuation; MINOR	3
	substitution; MINOR	mistranslation; MINOR	2
	substitution; MINOR	substitution; NEUTRAL	2
	grammar; NEUTRAL	capitalisation; MINOR	1
	grammar; NEUTRAL	textual conventions; MINOR	1
	grammar; MINOR	punctuation; NEUTRAL	1
	grammar; NEUTRAL	language register; NEUTRAL	1
	punctuation; MINOR	addition; NEUTRAL	1
	mistranslation; MINOR	deletion; MINOR	1
	substitution; MINOR		
	unidiomatic style; MINOR		
	grammar; MINOR		
	substitution; NEUTRAL		
	substitution; NEUTRAL		
	substitution; MINOR		
	substitution; MINOR		
	punctuation; MINOR		
	capitalisation; MINOR		
	textual conventions; MINOR		
	punctuation; NEUTRAL		
	language register; NEUTRAL		
	mistranslation; MINOR		

	substitution; MINOR		
	grammar; MINOR		
	addition; NEUTRAL		
	punctuation; MINOR		
	deletion; MINOR		

<p>We have here (grammar; NEUTRAL) our new Ibi 3 (substitution; MAJOR) which, in line with our electrics (textual conventions; NEUTRAL), carries (unidiomatic style; MINOR) Kia's 10 recycled (mistranslation; MINOR) materials (punctuation; NEUTRAL) in our commitment to be more sustainable and to take care of also of (grammar; NEUTRAL) the 2nd (insertion; MINOR) environment. They have 1 (substitution; MINOR) bitono (untranslated; MAJOR) upholstery made of vegan leather (punctuation; MINOR) (omission; MINOR) also carry (unidiomatic style; MINOR) elements characteristic of the pet (mistranslation; MAJOR), which is the most (omission; MAJOR) plastic in the world. This material is also in the roof covering (wrong term; MAJOR) (punctuation; MINOR) at (grammar; MINOR) the doors (mistranslation; MINOR) ,in harmony (grammar; NEUTRAL) with Kia's 10 recycled (mistranslation; MINOR) materials (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) the seats are very comfortable,(punctuation; MINOR) you (capitalisation; MINOR) can adjust them to be as best suits you (textual conventions; MINOR). You also have 2 (inconsistent with external reference; NEUTRAL) memory positions in case you have to swap cars with someone else (punctuation; NEUTRAL) and the option of having both heated seats as ventilated (textual conventions; MINOR) to adapt to any climatic situation (mistranslation; MINOR) (punctuation; MINOR) (deletion; MINOR)</p>	<p>grammar; NEUTRAL</p>		
		<p>grammar; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>3</p>
	<p>substitution; MAJOR</p>	<p>substitution; MAJOR</p>	<p>1</p>
	<p>textual conventions; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>textual conventions; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>1</p>
	<p>unidiomatic style; MINOR</p>	<p>unidiomatic style; MINOR</p>	<p>2</p>
	<p>mistranslation; MINOR</p>	<p>mistranslation; MINOR</p>	<p>4</p>
	<p>punctuation; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>punctuation; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>2</p>
	<p>grammar; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>insertion; MINOR</p>	<p>1</p>
	<p>insertion; MINOR</p>	<p>substitution; MINOR</p>	<p>1</p>
	<p>substitution; MINOR</p>	<p>untranslated; MAJOR</p>	<p>1</p>
	<p>untranslated; MAJOR</p>	<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>	<p>5</p>
	<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>	<p>omission; MINOR</p>	<p>1</p>
	<p>omission; MINOR</p>	<p>mistranslation; MAJOR</p>	<p>1</p>
	<p>unidiomatic style; MINOR</p>	<p>omission; MAJOR</p>	<p>1</p>
	<p>mistranslation; MAJOR</p>	<p>wrong term; MAJOR</p>	<p>1</p>
	<p>omission; MAJOR</p>	<p>grammar; MINOR</p>	<p>1</p>
	<p>wrong term; MAJOR</p>	<p>capitalisation; MINOR</p>	<p>2</p>
	<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>	<p>textual conventions; MINOR</p>	<p>2</p>
	<p>grammar; MINOR</p>	<p>inconsistent with external referenc</p>	<p>1</p>
	<p>mistranslation; MINOR</p>	<p>deletion; MINOR</p>	<p>1</p>
	<p>grammar; NEUTRAL</p>		
	<p>mistranslation; MINOR</p>		
	<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>		
	<p>capitalisation; MINOR</p>		
	<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>		
	<p>capitalisation; MINOR</p>		
	<p>textual conventions; MINOR</p>		
	<p>inconsistent with external reference; NEUTRAL</p>		
	<p>punctuation; NEUTRAL</p>		

	textual conventions; MINOR		
	mistranslation; MINOR		
	punctuation; MINOR		
	deletion; MINOR		

<p>The trunk of the IBI 3 (substitution; MAJOR) is 1 (substitution; MINOR) of the largest in its segment with 460l (inconsistent with external reference; NEUTRAL) of capacity (awkward style; NEUTRAL) (punctuation; MINOR) Apart from that (punctuation; NEUTRAL) it has 1 (substitution; MINOR) double bottom (punctuation; NEUTRAL)so we can have (grammar; NEUTRAL) the tray above (grammar; MINOR) and use the compartment below to store the (grammar; NEUTRAL) charging cables (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) AND if you need more space.(punctuation; NEUTRAL) you bring it down (awkward style; NEUTRAL) and you have all this extra space available. It is (language register; NEUTRAL) not only the trunk (awkward style; MINOR) (punctuation; NEUTRAL) but also the interior space (punctuation; MINOR)The rear seats allow 3 (substitution; NEUTRAL) occupants to travel with maximum comfort (punctuation; NEUTRAL) and the front space (punctuation; MINOR) with its sliding tray (punctuation; MINOR) offers 1 (substitution; MINOR) extra comfort to drivers. And lastly mention (textual conventions; MINOR) (punctuation; NEUTRAL) this car also has 1 (substitution; MINOR) Frank (substitution; MINOR) or front trunk (punctuation; NEUTRAL) (grammar; MINOR) up to 25 l (inconsistent with external reference; NEUTRAL) capacity to accommodate (awkward style; NEUTRAL) (punctuation; NEUTRAL) for example (punctuation; NEUTRAL) 1 (substitution; MINOR) charging cable. (deletion; MINOR)</p>	<p>substitution; MAJOR</p>		
	<p>substitution; MAJOR</p>	<p>substitution; MAJOR</p>	<p>1</p>
	<p>substitution; MINOR</p>	<p>substitution; MINOR</p>	<p>6</p>
	<p>inconsistent with external reference; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>inconsistent with external referenc</p>	<p>2</p>
	<p>awkward style; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>awkward style; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>3</p>
	<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>	<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>	<p>5</p>
	<p>punctuation; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>punctuation; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>9</p>
	<p>substitution; MINOR</p>	<p>grammar; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>2</p>
	<p>punctuation; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>grammar; MINOR</p>	<p>2</p>
	<p>grammar; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>capitalisation; MINOR</p>	<p>1</p>
	<p>grammar; MINOR</p>	<p>language register; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>1</p>
	<p>grammar; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>awkward style; MINOR</p>	<p>1</p>
	<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>	<p>substitution; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>1</p>
	<p>capitalisation; MINOR</p>	<p>textual conventions; MINOR</p>	<p>1</p>
	<p>punctuation; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>deletion; MINOR</p>	<p>1</p>
	<p>awkward style; NEUTRAL</p>		
	<p>language register; NEUTRAL</p>		
	<p>awkward style; MINOR</p>		
	<p>punctuation; NEUTRAL</p>		
	<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>		
	<p>substitution; NEUTRAL</p>		
	<p>punctuation; NEUTRAL</p>		
	<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>		
	<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>		
	<p>substitution; MINOR</p>		
	<p>textual conventions; MINOR</p>		
	<p>punctuation; NEUTRAL</p>		
	<p>substitution; MINOR</p>		
	<p>substitution; MINOR</p>		

	punctuation; NEUTRAL		
	grammar; MINOR		
	inconsistent with external reference; NEUTRAL		
	awkward style; NEUTRAL		
	punctuation; NEUTRAL		
	punctuation; NEUTRAL		
	substitution; MINOR		
	deletion; MINOR		

<p>How does your driving affect to (grammar; MINOR) the autonomy (wrong term; MAJOR) of the electric vehicle? As (grammar; NEUTRAL) with combustion vehicles, if you have 1 (substitution; MINOR) energetic conduction (mistranslation; MINOR) it will descend (grammar; MINOR). On the contrary (awkward style; NEUTRAL), drives efficiently (grammar; MINOR), autonomy (wrong term; MAJOR) will increase. For more detailed information (punctuation; NEUTRAL) you will be able to (awkward style; NEUTRAL) use (grammar; MINOR) the central screen (inconsistent with terminology resource; MINOR). In Ella (substitution; MINOR) you will be able to see the total autonomy (wrong term; MAJOR), in this case 377km. We have covered 782km and we have 1 (substitution; MINOR) 2nd (substitution; MINOR) consumption of 16.9kW after (grammar; MINOR) 100km. Finally, in the lower central space (punctuation; NEUTRAL) I need to (mistranslation; MINOR) see the instant consumption bar. In Ella (substitution; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) it will show us (punctuation; NEUTRAL) in a very graphic way (unidiomatic style; MINOR) . (punctuation; MINOR) the consumption we make, (punctuation; MINOR) so much for (mistranslation; MINOR) stepping on the accelerator, (punctuation; MINOR) more or less (punctuation; MINOR) if we carry (grammar; MINOR) air conditioning. (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) If we are climbing 1 (substitution; MINOR) mountain.(punctuation; MINOR) To have (grammar; MINOR) 1 (substitution; MINOR) idea super clear (substitution; MINOR) about how much we are consuming, Kia's boot (substitution; MAJOR) system will allow you to reflect (grammar; MINOR) consumption data from the point you determine (punctuation; MINOR) at (grammar; MINOR) the start of the trip, since the last recharge (punctuation; MINOR) or since you bought the vehicle (punctuation; MINOR) Kia (deletion; MINOR)</p>	<p>grammar; MINOR</p>		
	<p>grammar; MINOR</p>	<p>grammar; MINOR</p>	<p>9</p>
	<p>wrong term; MAJOR</p>	<p>wrong term; MAJOR</p>	<p>3</p>
	<p>grammar; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>grammar; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>1</p>
	<p>substitution; MINOR</p>	<p>substitution; MINOR</p>	<p>8</p>
	<p>mistranslation; MINOR</p>	<p>mistranslation; MINOR</p>	<p>3</p>
	<p>grammar; MINOR</p>	<p>awkward style; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>2</p>
	<p>awkward style; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>punctuation; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>3</p>
	<p>grammar; MINOR</p>	<p>inconsistent with terminology resource</p>	<p>1</p>
	<p>wrong term; MAJOR</p>	<p>capitalisation; MINOR</p>	<p>2</p>
	<p>punctuation; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>unidiomatic style; MINOR</p>	<p>1</p>
	<p>awkward style; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>	<p>9</p>
	<p>grammar; MINOR</p>	<p>substitution; MAJOR</p>	<p>1</p>
	<p>inconsistent with terminology resource; MINOR</p>	<p>deletion; MINOR</p>	<p>1</p>
	<p>substitution; MINOR</p>		
	<p>wrong term; MAJOR</p>		
	<p>substitution; MINOR</p>		
	<p>substitution; MINOR</p>		
	<p>grammar; MINOR</p>		
	<p>punctuation; NEUTRAL</p>		
	<p>mistranslation; MINOR</p>		
	<p>substitution; MINOR</p>		
	<p>capitalisation; MINOR</p>		
	<p>punctuation; NEUTRAL</p>		
	<p>unidiomatic style; MINOR</p>		
	<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>		

	punctuation; MINOR		
	mistranslation; MINOR		
	punctuation; MINOR		
	punctuation; MINOR		
	grammar; MINOR		
	punctuation; MINOR		
	capitalisation; MINOR		
	substitution; MINOR		
	punctuation; MINOR		
	grammar; MINOR		
	substitution; MINOR		
	substitution; MINOR		
	substitution; MAJOR		
	grammar; MINOR		
	punctuation; MINOR		
	grammar; MINOR		
	punctuation; MINOR		
	punctuation; MINOR		
	deletion; MINOR		

<p>Today we will see (grammar; NEUTRAL) how to charge your electric vehicle or plug-in connector (wrong term; MAJOR). In this case (punctuation; NEUTRAL) we are (language register; NEUTRAL) with 1 (substitution; MINOR) eniro (substitution; MAJOR). It has the front cover (undertranslation; MINOR), (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) there are other vehicles that can (grammar; NEUTRAL) have it on the side left front (grammar; MINOR) or on the right left side (mistranslation; MINOR). With the car open (grammar; MINOR), we will have to open the front portal (wrong term; MINOR). Let's find (grammar; MINOR) both (grammar; NEUTRAL) slow and fast charging (grammar; MINOR) . The slow one (awkward style; MINOR) will deal with (unidiomatic style; MINOR) only 1 (substitution; MINOR) of the holes (wrong term; MINOR) and fast charging (awkward style; MINOR), the 2 (inconsistent with external reference; NEUTRAL) holes (wrong term; MINOR). You will have to go to (grammar; NEUTRAL) a charger. There will be free chargers, which directly you will connect your charger (grammar; MINOR) and the load (wrong term; MINOR) will start, or there will be payment chargers (awkward style; MINOR), which (grammar; NEUTRAL) you will have to use the platform or card required by the charger (grammar; NEUTRAL). You must take it, introduce (grammar; MINOR) it (punctuation; NEUTRAL) and close the vehicle. You will hear 1 (substitution; MINOR) little Black (substitution; CRITICAL) which will confirm that the load (wrong term; MINOR) has started. You will be able to see on the headlights (mistranslation; MAJOR) that the load (wrong term; MINOR) is initiated (grammar; MINOR), as you will see that they are gradually increasing (textual conventions; MINOR) and also on the interior infraexperiment (substitution; MAJOR) screen (punctuation; MINOR)(deletion; MINOR)</p>	<p>grammar; NEUTRAL</p>		
	<p>grammar; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>grammar; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>6</p>
	<p>wrong term; MAJOR</p>	<p>wrong term; MAJOR</p>	<p>1</p>
	<p>punctuation; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>punctuation; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>2</p>
	<p>language register; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>language register; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>1</p>
	<p>substitution; MINOR</p>	<p>substitution; MINOR</p>	<p>3</p>
	<p>substitution; MAJOR</p>	<p>substitution; MAJOR</p>	<p>2</p>
	<p>undertranslation; MINOR</p>	<p>undertranslation; MINOR</p>	<p>1</p>
	<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>	<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>	<p>2</p>
	<p>capitalisation; MINOR</p>	<p>capitalisation; MINOR</p>	<p>1</p>
	<p>grammar; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>grammar; MINOR</p>	<p>7</p>
	<p>grammar; MINOR</p>	<p>mistranslation; MINOR</p>	<p>1</p>
	<p>mistranslation; MINOR</p>	<p>wrong term; MINOR</p>	<p>6</p>
	<p>grammar; MINOR</p>	<p>awkward style; MINOR</p>	<p>3</p>
	<p>wrong term; MINOR</p>	<p>unidiomatic style; MINOR</p>	<p>1</p>
	<p>grammar; MINOR</p>	<p>inconsistent with external referenc</p>	<p>1</p>
	<p>grammar; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>substitution; CRITICAL</p>	<p>1</p>
	<p>grammar; MINOR</p>	<p>mistranslation; MAJOR</p>	<p>1</p>
	<p>awkward style; MINOR</p>	<p>textual conventions; MINOR</p>	<p>1</p>
	<p>unidiomatic style; MINOR</p>	<p>deletion; MINOR</p>	<p>1</p>
	<p>substitution; MINOR</p>		<p>0</p>
	<p>wrong term; MINOR</p>		
	<p>awkward style; MINOR</p>		
	<p>inconsistent with external reference; NEUTRAL</p>		

	wrong term; MINOR		
	grammar; NEUTRAL		
	grammar; MINOR		
	wrong term; MINOR		
	awkward style; MINOR		
	grammar; NEUTRAL		
	grammar; NEUTRAL		
	grammar; MINOR		
	punctuation; NEUTRAL		
	substitution; MINOR		
	substitution; CRITICAL		
	wrong term; MINOR		
	mistranslation; MAJOR		
	wrong term; MINOR		
	grammar; MINOR		
	textual conventions; MINOR		
	substitution; MAJOR		
	punctuation; MINOR		
	deletion; MINOR		

<p>Hello (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) Hello (punctuation; MINOR) In this house tour (substitution; MINOR) we are going to explain what to do if your TV's solar controller (undertranslation; NEUTRAL) doesn't respond (grammar; MINOR) (punctuation; MINOR) Let's start (grammar; NEUTRAL) (punctuation; MINOR) The first thing we need to do is to check if the controller is charged and connected via Bluetooth to the TV (grammar; MINOR) (punctuation; MINOR) How (punctuation; MINOR) to Stay near the TV (grammar; MINOR) and simultaneously press the (capitalisation; MINOR) return buttons Play pause A few seconds (grammar; MINOR) (punctuation; MINOR) The TV should match (mistranslation; MINOR) the controller (undertranslation; NEUTRAL) and show (grammar; NEUTRAL) the battery charge status, (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) otherwise (grammar; NEUTRAL) if it does not (language register; NEUTRAL) match (mistranslation; MINOR) or is downloaded (mistranslation; MINOR). (punctuation; MINOR) Remember that you can charge it with indoor or outdoor light (punctuation; MINOR) with 1 (substitution; MINOR) USB type c (capitalisation; MINOR) charger (punctuation; NEUTRAL) like the one on (grammar; MINOR) your cell (unidiomatic style; MINOR) phone, or by absorbing RF waves (punctuation; NEUTRAL) like those of the router (grammar; MINOR) (punctuation; MINOR) hat (grammar; MINOR) transforms them into energy (mistranslation; MINOR) (grammar; MINOR) and charges it (grammar; MINOR) I hope this info has gotten you out of trouble. (awkward style; NEUTRAL) See (capitalisation; NEUTRAL) you in 1 (substitution; MINOR) next house tour.(substitution; MINOR)</p>	<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>	<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>	<p>11</p>
	capitalisation; MINOR	capitalisation; MINOR	4
	punctuation; MINOR	substitution; MINOR	4
	substitution; MINOR	undertranslation; NEUTRAL	2
	undertranslation; NEUTRAL	grammar; MINOR	9
	grammar; MINOR	grammar; NEUTRAL	3
	punctuation; MINOR	mistranslation; MINOR	4
	grammar; NEUTRAL	language register; NEUTRAL	1
	punctuation; MINOR	punctuation; NEUTRAL	2
	grammar; MINOR	unidiomatic style; MINOR	1
	punctuation; MINOR	awkward style; NEUTRAL	1
	punctuation; MINOR	capitalisation; NEUTRAL	1
	grammar; MINOR		
	capitalisation; MINOR		
	grammar; MINOR		
	punctuation; MINOR		
	mistranslation; MINOR		
	undertranslation; NEUTRAL		
	grammar; NEUTRAL		
	punctuation; MINOR		
	capitalisation; MINOR		
	grammar; NEUTRAL		
	language register; NEUTRAL		
	mistranslation; MINOR		
	mistranslation; MINOR		
	punctuation; MINOR		
	punctuation; MINOR		
	substitution; MINOR		

	capitalisation; MINOR		
	punctuation; NEUTRAL		
	grammar; MINOR		
	unidiomatic style; MINOR		
	punctuation; NEUTRAL		
	grammar; MINOR		
	punctuation; MINOR		
	grammar; MINOR		
	mistranslation; MINOR		
	grammar; MINOR		
	grammar; MINOR		
	awkward style; NEUTRAL		
	capitalisation; NEUTRAL		
	substitution; MINOR		
	substitution; MINOR		

<p>Hello, hello! Today I'm going to show you how to update your TV software with 1 (substitution; MINOR) USB from Samsung's website (grammar; NEUTRAL). The first thing you will (language register; NEUTRAL) have to do is to grammar; MINOR) select the menu, punctuation; MINOR)(capitalisation; MINOR) you will (language register; NEUTRAL) mark (mistranslation; MINOR) configuration (capitalisation; MINOR)(inconsistent with terminology resource; MINOR), assistance (inconsistent with terminology resource; MINOR) punctuation; MINOR)(capitalisation; MINOR) and we mark (mistranslation; MINOR) about this TV (capitalisation; MINOR). Verify your TV (grammar; NEUTRAL) code and (grammar; NEUTRAL) software version. Remember this information (grammar; NEUTRAL) as they are going (language register; NEUTRAL) to be very important. (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) When you go to Samsung's website (language register; NEUTRAL) and download the latest software version from your TV (grammar; MINOR), (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) decompresses (mistranslation; MINOR) the file and save it in the top level unidiomatic style; MINOR) folder of the unit USB (inconsistent with terminology resource; MINOR) connected to your PC. Follow these steps (punctuation; NEUTRAL) because otherwise the TV will not be able to locate the upgrade (inconsistent with terminology resource; NEUTRAL) package. Insert the external USB drive in (grammar; NEUTRAL) the slot designed (grammar; NEUTRAL) for these TV devices (grammar; MINOR). 1 (substitution; MINOR) time performed (mistranslation; MINOR) these steps (grammar; MINOR), you must go to (capitalisation; MINOR), configuration (inconsistent with terminology resource; MINOR), support (inconsistent with terminology resource; MINOR) software (capitalisation; MINOR) (omission; MINOR) (punctuation; NEUTRAL) and update(capitalisation; MINOR) now. Importantly, (grammar; MINOR) do not turn off the TV or remove this unit (inconsistent with terminology resource; MINOR).(punctuation; MINOR) USB until the upgrade (omission; MINOR) (punctuation; MINOR) Done! (mistranslation; MINOR)</p>	<p>substitution; MINOR</p>	<p>substitution; MINOR</p>	<p>2</p>
	grammar; NEUTRAL	grammar; NEUTRAL	6
	language register; NEUTRAL	language register; NEUTRAL	4
	capitalisation; MINOR	capitalisation; MINOR	9
	language register; NEUTRAL	mistranslation; MINOR	5
	mistranslation; MINOR	inconsistent with terminology reso	6
	capitalisation; MINOR	punctuation; MINOR	4
	inconsistent with terminology resource; MINOR	grammar; MINOR	4
	inconsistent with terminology resource; MINOR	punctuation; NEUTRAL	2
	capitalisation; MINOR	inconsistent with terminology reso	1
	mistranslation; MINOR	omission; MINOR	2
	capitalisation; MINOR		
	grammar; NEUTRAL		
	grammar; NEUTRAL		
	grammar; NEUTRAL		
	language register; NEUTRAL		
	punctuation; MINOR		
	capitalisation; MINOR		
	language register; NEUTRAL		
	grammar; MINOR		
	punctuation; MINOR		
	capitalisation; MINOR		
	mistranslation; MINOR		

	inconsistent with terminology resource; MINOR		
	punctuation; NEUTRAL		
	inconsistent with terminology resource; NEUTRAL		
	grammar; NEUTRAL		
	grammar; NEUTRAL		
	grammar; MINOR		
	substitution; MINOR		
	mistranslation; MINOR		
	grammar; MINOR		
	capitalisation; MINOR		
	inconsistent with terminology resource; MINOR		
	inconsistent with terminology resource; MINOR		
	capitalisation; MINOR		
	omission; MINOR		
	punctuation; NEUTRAL		
	capitalisation; MINOR		
	grammar; MINOR		
	inconsistent with terminology resource; MINOR		
	punctuation; MINOR		
	omission; MINOR		
	punctuation; MINOR		
	mistranslation; MINOR		

<p>Hello (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) Hello! Today we are going to comment (mistranslation; MINOR) the benefits of having 1 (substitution; MINOR) TV with intelligence artificial (grammar; MINOR). Shall we start? (substitution; NEUTRAL) The new television processors Samsung (textual conventions; MINOR) with artificial intelligence identify our habits of consumption (awkward style; MINOR) to adapt to what weseee (mistranslation; MINOR) and improve (grammar; NEUTRAL) quality. It not only corrects defects, but it is a learning process. (punctuation; MINOR) by which it improves (grammar; NEUTRAL) image and sound. How do I benefit from it? Samsung TVs now make adjustments to give you a clearer view of your sports. (punctuation; MINOR) favorites (textual conventions; MINOR). For example, in 1 (substitution; MINOR) tennis match (punctuation; NEUTRAL) (grammar; MINOR) will offer better quality ball movement (grammar; NEUTRAL) so you don't miss any detail (grammar; MINOR) (punctuation; MINOR) Thanks to the skeling app. (substitution; MAJOR) (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) Even having lower quality than the TV resolution (textual conventions; MINOR), the VA (substitution; MINOR) TV to rescue (substitution; MINOR) the content you are watching at 8k (inconsistent with external reference; NEUTRAL) (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR)and no weird noises. The TV is responsible for (mistranslation; MINOR) improving the audio of 1 (substitution; MINOR) dialogue (awkward style; MINOR) without distorting the sound of the whole scene (punctuation; MINOR), Hey hey! (substitution; MAJOR) Energy mode (capitalisation; MINOR), which ensures that the television (language register; MINOR) optimizes the lighting (wrong term; MINOR) depending on the content we are watching. It is (language register; NEUTRAL) up to you to choose in which range (textual conventions; NEUTRAL) of televisions you will (language register; NEUTRAL) enjoy these incredible results. It is clear to us (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) neog LED (spelling; MINOR) 8 k (inconsistent with external reference; NEUTRAL) (punctuation; MINOR) because it has the most advanced processors (punctuation; MINOR)</p>	<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>	<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>	<p>10</p>
<p>capitalisation; MINOR</p>	<p>capitalisation; MINOR</p>	<p>capitalisation; MINOR</p>	<p>5</p>
<p>mistranslation; MINOR</p>	<p>mistranslation; MINOR</p>	<p>mistranslation; MINOR</p>	<p>3</p>
<p>substitution; MINOR</p>	<p>substitution; MINOR</p>	<p>substitution; MINOR</p>	<p>5</p>
<p>grammar; MINOR</p>	<p>grammar; MINOR</p>	<p>grammar; MINOR</p>	<p>3</p>
<p>substitution; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>substitution; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>substitution; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>1</p>
<p>textual conventions; MINOR</p>	<p>textual conventions; MINOR</p>	<p>textual conventions; MINOR</p>	<p>3</p>
<p>awkward style; MINOR</p>	<p>awkward style; MINOR</p>	<p>awkward style; MINOR</p>	<p>2</p>
<p>mistranslation; MINOR</p>	<p>grammar; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>grammar; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>3</p>
<p>grammar; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>punctuation; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>punctuation; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>1</p>
<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>	<p>substitution; MAJOR</p>	<p>substitution; MAJOR</p>	<p>2</p>
<p>grammar; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>inconsistent with external referenc</p>	<p>inconsistent with external referenc</p>	<p>2</p>
<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>	<p>language register; MINOR</p>	<p>language register; MINOR</p>	<p>1</p>
<p>textual conventions; MINOR</p>	<p>wrong term; MINOR</p>	<p>wrong term; MINOR</p>	<p>1</p>
<p>substitution; MINOR</p>	<p>language register; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>language register; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>2</p>
<p>punctuation; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>textual conventions; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>textual conventions; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>1</p>
<p>grammar; MINOR</p>	<p>spelling; MINOR</p>	<p>spelling; MINOR</p>	<p>1</p>
<p>grammar; NEUTRAL</p>	<p></p>	<p></p>	<p></p>
<p>grammar; MINOR</p>	<p></p>	<p></p>	<p></p>
<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>	<p></p>	<p></p>	<p></p>
<p>substitution; MAJOR</p>	<p></p>	<p></p>	<p></p>
<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>	<p></p>	<p></p>	<p></p>
<p>capitalisation; MINOR</p>	<p></p>	<p></p>	<p></p>
<p>textual conventions; MINOR</p>	<p></p>	<p></p>	<p></p>

	substitution; MINOR		
	substitution; MINOR		
	inconsistent with external reference; NEUTRAL		
	punctuation; MINOR		
	capitalisation; MINOR		
	mistranslation; MINOR		
	substitution; MINOR		
	awkward style; MINOR		
	punctuation; MINOR		
	substitution; MAJOR		
	capitalisation; MINOR		
	language register; MINOR		
	wrong term; MINOR		
	language register; NEUTRAL		
	textual conventions; NEUTRAL		
	language register; NEUTRAL		
	punctuation; MINOR		
	capitalisation; MINOR		
	spelling; MINOR		
	inconsistent with external reference; NEUTRAL		
	punctuation; MINOR		
	punctuation; MINOR		

<p>Hello, (punctuation; MINOR)Hello! In this house tour (substitution; MINOR) (punctuation; MINOR) I'm going to show you how to add your Samsung TV to the Smart Things (substitution; MINOR) app to control your home's smart devices (grammar; NEUTRAL). It is (language register; NEUTRAL) compatible with 1 (substitution; MINOR) lot of (grammar; MINOR) brands, in addition to (language register; NEUTRAL) Samsung's virtual assistants, Google and Amazon (mistranslation; MINOR). And to add your TV to Smart Things (substitution; MINOR) (punctuation; MINOR) you can do it through registration automatic or manual (grammar; MINOR), but remember, always has to be (grammar; NEUTRAL) connected to the (capitalisation; NEUTRAL) Internet. For automatic registration, activate the application (language register; MINOR) and log in with your Samsung account. You will see how it detects nearby Smart TVs and 1 (substitution; MINOR) (omission; MINOR) pop-up window will appear. When you see that (punctuation; MINOR) it asks you to (capitalisation; MINOR) add the TV, click (grammar; NEUTRAL) (capitalisation; MINOR) add now, press start (wrong term; MINOR) and select capitalisation; MINOR) location and room. (capitalisation; MINOR) (grammar; NEUTRAL) if the Smart Things (substitution; MINOR) app does not (language register; NEUTRAL) detect your TV automatically, you can register it manually. Turn on your TV and start (grammar; NEUTRAL) the Smart Things (substitution; MINOR) app. 1 (substitution; MINOR) time inside, select t v (spelling; MINOR), marks (mistranslation; MINOR) the pin (spelling; MINOR) that appears on the TV screen and waits (grammar; MINOR) for the process to be completed (grammar; MINOR) and everything would be done (language register; MINOR). See you at (grammar; MINOR) the next house tour (substitution; MINOR)(punctuation; MINOR)</p>	<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>		
	punctuation; MINOR	punctuation; MINOR	5
	substitution; MINOR	substitution; MINOR	9
	punctuation; MINOR	grammar; NEUTRAL	5
	substitution; MINOR	language register; NEUTRAL	3
	grammar; NEUTRAL	grammar; MINOR	5
	language register; NEUTRAL	mistranslation; MINOR	2
	substitution; MINOR	capitalisation; NEUTRAL	1
	grammar; MINOR	language register; MINOR	2
	language register; NEUTRAL	omission; MINOR	1
	mistranslation; MINOR	capitalisation; MINOR	3
	substitution; MINOR	wrong term; MINOR	1
	punctuation; MINOR	spelling; MINOR	2
	grammar; MINOR		
	grammar; NEUTRAL		
	capitalisation; NEUTRAL		
	language register; MINOR		
	substitution; MINOR		
	omission; MINOR		
	punctuation; MINOR		
	capitalisation; MINOR		
	grammar; NEUTRAL		
	capitalisation; MINOR		
	wrong term; MINOR		
	capitalisation; MINOR		
	grammar; NEUTRAL		
	substitution; MINOR		

	language register; NEUTRAL		
	grammar; NEUTRAL		
	substitution; MINOR		
	substitution; MINOR		
	spelling; MINOR		
	mistranslation; MINOR		
	spelling; MINOR		
	grammar; MINOR		
	grammar; MINOR		
	language register; MINOR		
	grammar; MINOR		
	substitution; MINOR		
	punctuation; MINOR		

<p>Every step I take (awkward style; MINOR) and every stride I take is always full of 1 (substitution; MINOR) purpose (punctuation; MINOR) and 1 (substitution; MINOR) goal (punctuation; NEUTRAL) and 1 (substitution; MINOR) dream (grammar; NEUTRAL) I want to achieve. In general, in my day-to-day life, even if I'm not competing, I use meditation a lot (awkward style; MINOR) , but then just before painting (mistranslation; MINOR), I need to know how to concentrate (mistranslation; MINOR), (grammar; MINOR) be isolated. The Android (substitution; MAJOR) application is great for that (awkward style; NEUTRAL).(punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) With the Galaxy Bats that are milk (mistranslation; MINOR). With focus, with passion (punctuation; MINOR) you can achieve things you have never thought of before (mistranslation; MINOR) (punctuation; MINOR)</p>	<p>awkward style; MINOR</p>		
		<p>awkward style; MINOR</p>	<p>2</p>
	<p>substitution; MINOR</p>	<p>substitution; MINOR</p>	<p>3</p>
	<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>	<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>	<p>4</p>
	<p>substitution; MINOR</p>	<p>punctuation; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>1</p>
	<p>punctuation; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>grammar; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>1</p>
	<p>substitution; MINOR</p>	<p>mistranslation; MINOR</p>	<p>4</p>
	<p>grammar; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>grammar; MINOR</p>	<p>1</p>
	<p>awkward style; MINOR</p>	<p>substitution; MAJOR</p>	<p>1</p>
	<p>mistranslation; MINOR</p>	<p>awkward style; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>1</p>
	<p>mistranslation; MINOR</p>	<p>capitalisation; MINOR</p>	<p>1</p>
	<p>grammar; MINOR</p>		
	<p>substitution; MAJOR</p>		
	<p>awkward style; NEUTRAL</p>		
	<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>		
	<p>capitalisation; MINOR</p>		
	<p>mistranslation; MINOR</p>		
	<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>		
	<p>mistranslation; MINOR</p>		
	<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>		

<p>Who doesn't like to save 1 (substitution; MINOR) little money at IKEA(punctuation; MINOR) I tell you (unidiomatic style; MINOR). (punctuation; MINOR) we have (language register; MINOR) launched the (grammar; NEUTRAL) new rewards for IKEA family (capitalisation; MINOR) (punctuation; MINOR) which are the new advantages for (grammar; NEUTRAL) the club (punctuation; MINOR) Until now (punctuation; NEUTRAL) they (grammar; MINOR) had exclusive advantages (punctuation; MINOR) discounts (punctuation; NEUTRAL) and the famous free coffees. Now you can accumulate the (grammar; MINOR) points and spend them on whatever you want (punctuation; MINOR) in restaurants (mistranslation; MINOR) (punctuation; MINOR) (grammar; MINOR) services (punctuation; MINOR) in (grammar; MINOR) products (punctuation; MINOR) We go on (mistranslation; MINOR) anything within (capitalisation; MINOR) Ikea (punctuation; MINOR) For example (punctuation; NEUTRAL) for €5 purchase (unidiomatic style; MINOR) you get 1 (substitution; MINOR) point (punctuation; MINOR) but you can also accumulate points for many other things (punctuation; MINOR) like logging in on (grammar; NEUTRAL) the website (punctuation; MINOR) create (grammar; MINOR) 1 (substitution; MINOR) wishlist (punctuation; MINOR) come to 1 (substitution; MINOR) event in store (spelling; NEUTRAL) (unidiomatic style; NEUTRAL) among other things (punctuation; MINOR) And then you take your points and spend them on whatever you want (punctuation; MINOR) For example (punctuation; NEUTRAL) with 50 points you unlock 1 (substitution; MINOR) coupon of €5 (unidiomatic style; MINOR) for your next home delivery (punctuation; MINOR) Well nothing that points (mistranslation; MINOR) if you are (language register; NEUTRAL) not a member yet (punctuation; MINOR) you can get on the web (language register; NEUTRAL) (punctuation; MINOR) create 1 (substitution; MINOR) account very quickly and free (grammar; MINOR) (punctuation; NEUTRAL) and accumulate Chao points. (mistranslation; MINOR)</p>	<p>substitution; MINOR</p>		
	<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>	<p>substitution; MINOR</p>	<p>6</p>
	<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>	<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>	<p>19</p>
	<p>unidiomatic style; MINOR</p>	<p>unidiomatic style; MINOR</p>	<p>3</p>
	<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>	<p>language register; MINOR</p>	<p>1</p>
	<p>language register; MINOR</p>	<p>grammar; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>3</p>
	<p>grammar; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>capitalisation; MINOR</p>	<p>2</p>
	<p>capitalisation; MINOR</p>	<p>punctuation; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>5</p>
	<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>	<p>grammar; MINOR</p>	<p>6</p>
	<p>grammar; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>mistranslation; MINOR</p>	<p>4</p>
	<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>	<p>spelling; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>1</p>
	<p>punctuation; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>unidiomatic style; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>1</p>
	<p>grammar; MINOR</p>	<p>language register; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>2</p>
	<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>		
	<p>punctuation; NEUTRAL</p>		
	<p>grammar; MINOR</p>		
	<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>		
	<p>mistranslation; MINOR</p>		
	<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>		
	<p>grammar; MINOR</p>		
	<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>		
	<p>grammar; MINOR</p>		
	<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>		
	<p>mistranslation; MINOR</p>		
	<p>capitalisation; MINOR</p>		
	<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>		

	punctuation; NEUTRAL		
	unidiomatic style; MINOR		
	substitution; MINOR		
	punctuation; MINOR		
	punctuation; MINOR		
	grammar; NEUTRAL		
	punctuation; MINOR		
	grammar; MINOR		
	substitution; MINOR		
	punctuation; MINOR		
	substitution; MINOR		
	spelling; NEUTRAL		
	unidiomatic style; NEUTRAL		
	punctuation; MINOR		
	punctuation; MINOR		
	punctuation; NEUTRAL		
	substitution; MINOR		
	unidiomatic style; MINOR		
	punctuation; MINOR		
	mistranslation; MINOR		
	language register; NEUTRAL		
	punctuation; MINOR		
	language register; NEUTRAL		
	punctuation; MINOR		
	substitution; MINOR		
	grammar; MINOR		
	punctuation; NEUTRAL		
	mistranslation; MINOR		

<p>When you come to IKEA to choose 1 (substitution; MINOR) new mattress (punctuation; MINOR) you always ask us what it should be like. Well (punctuation; MINOR) today I'll tell you about it (awkward style; MINOR). The first thing you need to know is whether you are going to sleep (grammar; NEUTRAL) alone or accompanied (unidiomatic style; MINOR). If you sleep as a couple and one of the 2 (substitution; NEUTRAL) moves a lot because it doesn't fit, watch out! (substitution; MINOR) 1 (substitution; MINOR) bagged spring mattress (inconsistent with terminology resource; MINOR) is the best option (punctuation; MINOR) and if you like to sleep snuggled (grammar; NEUTRAL) up without moving too much, 1 (substitution; MINOR) viscoelastic mattress (inconsistent with terminology resource; MINOR) will hug you all night long. The second (grammar; NEUTRAL) is to choose the firmness of the mattress. If you always sleep Face (capitalisation; MINOR) up (grammar; NEUTRAL) or sideways (grammar; MINOR) and you (awkward style; NEUTRAL) weigh more than 85 kilos (inconsistent with external reference; NEUTRAL), we recommend you choose (grammar; NEUTRAL) 1 (substitution; MINOR) extra firm mattress (punctuation; MINOR) and if you sleep face down (grammar; NEUTRAL) or sideways (grammar; MINOR) and weigh less than 85 kilos (inconsistent with external reference; NEUTRAL), the best option is to choose 1 (substitution; MINOR) mattress with less firmness (unidiomatic style; MINOR) that adapts to your body. Finally, choose the size of the mattress well.(punctuation; MINOR) and don't forget to fix (mistranslation; MINOR) your pillow perfect (grammar; MINOR) so that dreams do not end prematurely (unidiomatic style; MINOR) .(punctuation; MINOR)</p>	<p>substitution; MINOR</p>		
	<p>substitution; MINOR</p>	<p>substitution; MINOR</p>	<p>6</p>
	<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>	<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>	<p>6</p>
	<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>	<p>awkward style; MINOR</p>	<p>1</p>
	<p>awkward style; MINOR</p>	<p>grammar; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>6</p>
	<p>grammar; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>unidiomatic style; MINOR</p>	<p>3</p>
	<p>unidiomatic style; MINOR</p>	<p>substitution; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>1</p>
	<p>substitution; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>inconsistent with terminology resource</p>	<p>2</p>
	<p>substitution; MINOR</p>	<p>capitalisation; MINOR</p>	<p>1</p>
	<p>substitution; MINOR</p>	<p>grammar; MINOR</p>	<p>3</p>
	<p>inconsistent with terminology resource; MINOR</p>	<p>awkward style; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>1</p>
	<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>	<p>inconsistent with external reference</p>	<p>2</p>
	<p>grammar; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>mistranslation; MINOR</p>	<p>1</p>
	<p>substitution; MINOR</p>		
	<p>inconsistent with terminology resource; MINOR</p>		
	<p>grammar; NEUTRAL</p>		
	<p>capitalisation; MINOR</p>		
	<p>grammar; NEUTRAL</p>		
	<p>grammar; MINOR</p>		
	<p>awkward style; NEUTRAL</p>		
	<p>inconsistent with external reference; NEUTRAL</p>		
	<p>grammar; NEUTRAL</p>		
	<p>substitution; MINOR</p>		
	<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>		
	<p>grammar; NEUTRAL</p>		
	<p>grammar; MINOR</p>		

	inconsistent with external reference; NEUTRAL		
	substitution; MINOR		
	unidiomatic style; MINOR		
	punctuation; MINOR		
	mistranslation; MINOR		
	grammar; MINOR		
	unidiomatic style; MINOR		
	punctuation; MINOR		

<p>If lately (grammar; NEUTRAL) you don't consult (mistranslation; MINOR) your pillow at all because it's a little bit (grammar; NEUTRAL) (deletion; MINOR), (grammar; MINOR) is that (grammar; NEUTRAL) you haven't given him (grammar; MINOR) all the love he (grammar; MINOR) deserved. The most important thing for 1 (substitution; MINOR) pillow to last a long time is that the stuffing (grammar; NEUTRAL), as well as (grammar; MINOR) comfortable, is (omission; MAJOR) and absorbs moisture. And as a second piece of advice (awkward style; NEUTRAL), before putting (grammar; NEUTRAL) the cover of the sheet set on them (awkward style; MINOR), always use protective pillowcases. You can use 1 (substitution; MINOR) basic like this or 1 (substitution; MINOR) thermal (grammar; MINOR), which (grammar; MINOR) (punctuation; MINOR) according to (awkward style; NEUTRAL) the color of each side (punctuation; MINOR) it gives you cooler weather in summer or warmer weather in winter (mistranslation; MINOR). With these tips (punctuation; MINOR)</p>	<p>grammar; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>grammar; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>5</p>
	mistranslation; MINOR	mistranslation; MINOR	2
	grammar; NEUTRAL	deletion; MINOR	1
	deletion; MINOR	grammar; MINOR	6
	grammar; MINOR	substitution; MINOR	3
	grammar; NEUTRAL	omission; MAJOR	1
	grammar; MINOR	awkward style; NEUTRAL	2
	grammar; MINOR	awkward style; MINOR	1
	substitution; MINOR	punctuation; MINOR	3
	grammar; NEUTRAL		
	grammar; MINOR		
	omission; MAJOR		
	awkward style; NEUTRAL		
	grammar; NEUTRAL		
	awkward style; MINOR		
	substitution; MINOR		
	substitution; MINOR		
	grammar; MINOR		
	grammar; MINOR		
	punctuation; MINOR		
	awkward style; NEUTRAL		
	punctuation; MINOR		
	mistranslation; MINOR		
	punctuation; MINOR		

<p>Do you also finish 1 (substitution; MINOR) coffee And (capitalisation; MINOR) you're already thinking about the next one? Then come upstairs (overtranslation; NEUTRAL) and have (mistranslation; MINOR) 1 (substitution; MINOR) Coffee (capitalisation; MINOR) corner with my favorite products. It's not coming on top (mistranslation; MINOR), and it is (language register; MINOR) not 1 (substitution; MINOR) Coffee(capitalisation; MINOR) corner if you don't have a great (undertranslation; MINOR) organizer to serve (grammar; NEUTRAL) as a canvas. (punctuation; MINOR) For (capitalisation; MINOR) everything else (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) you need 1 (substitution; MINOR) coffee maker and if it is (language register; NEUTRAL) also a teapot, better (unidiomatic style; MINOR). You also need a few (awkward style; NEUTRAL) aesthetic bottles (mistranslation; MINOR) (punctuation; NEUTRAL) and if you like coffee, take 2 (substitution; NEUTRAL) cups (punctuation; MINOR) or 3 (substitution; NEUTRAL) (punctuation; NEUTRAL) or 4 (substitution; NEUTRAL),(punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) now place (grammar; MINOR) 1 (substitution; MINOR) teaspoon (mistranslation; MINOR) for the milk and (grammar; NEUTRAL) teaspoons (punctuation; NEUTRAL) and finally, 1 (substitution; MINOR) aromatic (grammar; MINOR) candle. (omission; NEUTRAL) You have your (capitalisation; MINOR) Coffee corner! Now it's your turn to go even higher (mistranslation; MINOR) and share it on your social networks (punctuation; MINOR)(deletion; MINOR)</p>	<p>substitution; MINOR</p>	<p>substitution; MINOR</p>	<p>6</p>
	<p>capitalisation; MINOR</p>	<p>capitalisation; MINOR</p>	<p>7</p>
	<p>overtranslation; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>overtranslation; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>1</p>
	<p>mistranslation; MINOR</p>	<p>mistranslation; MINOR</p>	<p>5</p>
	<p>substitution; MINOR</p>	<p>language register; MINOR</p>	<p>1</p>
	<p>capitalisation; MINOR</p>	<p>undertranslation; MINOR</p>	<p>1</p>
	<p>mistranslation; MINOR</p>	<p>grammar; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>2</p>
	<p>language register; MINOR</p>	<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>	<p>5</p>
	<p>substitution; MINOR</p>	<p>language register; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>1</p>
	<p>capitalisation; MINOR</p>	<p>unidiomatic style; MINOR</p>	<p>1</p>
	<p>undertranslation; MINOR</p>	<p>awkward style; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>1</p>
	<p>grammar; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>punctuation; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>3</p>
	<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>	<p>substitution; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>3</p>
	<p>capitalisation; MINOR</p>	<p>grammar; MINOR</p>	<p>2</p>
	<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>	<p>omission; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>1</p>
	<p>capitalisation; MINOR</p>	<p>deletion; MINOR</p>	<p>1</p>
	<p>substitution; MINOR</p>		
	<p>language register; NEUTRAL</p>		
	<p>unidiomatic style; MINOR</p>		
	<p>awkward style; NEUTRAL</p>		
	<p>mistranslation; MINOR</p>		
	<p>punctuation; NEUTRAL</p>		
	<p>substitution; NEUTRAL</p>		
	<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>		
	<p>substitution; NEUTRAL</p>		
	<p>punctuation; NEUTRAL</p>		
	<p>substitution; NEUTRAL</p>		
	<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>		

	capitalisation; MINOR		
	grammar; MINOR		
	substitution; MINOR		
	mistranslation; MINOR		
	grammar; NEUTRAL		
	punctuation; NEUTRAL		
	substitution; MINOR		
	grammar; MINOR		
	omission; NEUTRAL		
	capitalisation; MINOR		
	mistranslation; MINOR		
	punctuation; MINOR		
	deletion; MINOR		

<p>Do you want to win the Mother (capitalisation; NEUTRAL) or Father (capitalisation; NEUTRAL) of the Year (capitalisation; NEUTRAL) award? (punctuation; MINOR) making (textual conventions; MINOR) your little one enjoy playing in your (mistranslation; MINOR) room? Then you have to move on (unidiomatic style; MINOR) from this to this. The first thing to do is to (awkward style; NEUTRAL) choose 1 (substitution; MINOR) area that does not (language register; NEUTRAL) interrupt (unidiomatic style; MINOR) El Paso (substitution; MINOR) .(punctuation; MINOR) and avoid (grammar; MINOR) problems. I have (language register; MINOR) chosen this one. Now it is (language register; NEUTRAL) time to choose 1 (substitution; MINOR) carpet fun (grammar; MINOR) to make the kids comfortable and warm (awkward style; NEUTRAL). Adds (grammar; MINOR) colourful seating areas, a few fun cushions is enough. Now comes the wildlife. Add as many stuffed animals as you consider (unidiomatic style; MINOR). It's good that the kids are getting familiar with the different animals (mistranslation; MINOR) (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) and (grammar; NEUTRAL) to develop their most creative part (unidiomatic style; MINOR), 1 (substitution; MINOR) easel for them to paint, draw (punctuation; NEUTRAL) or express themselves in their own way. And well, playing is very good very good (unidiomatic style; MINOR), but they also have to learn to pick up (unidiomatic style; MINOR), so 1 (substitution; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) Good (punctuation; MINOR) little box light and accessible (grammar; MINOR) is perfect for them to do it themselves. Now it's your turn (grammar; MINOR) enjoy time with them in their play area. Go for the award! (language register; NEUTRAL)</p>	<p>capitalisation; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>capitalisation; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>3</p>
	<p>capitalisation; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>	<p>4</p>
	<p>capitalisation; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>textual conventions; MINOR</p>	<p>1</p>
	<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>	<p>mistranslation; MINOR</p>	<p>2</p>
	<p>textual conventions; MINOR</p>	<p>unidiomatic style; MINOR</p>	<p>6</p>
	<p>mistranslation; MINOR</p>	<p>awkward style; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>2</p>
	<p>unidiomatic style; MINOR</p>	<p>substitution; MINOR</p>	<p>5</p>
	<p>awkward style; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>language register; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>3</p>
	<p>substitution; MINOR</p>	<p>grammar; MINOR</p>	<p>5</p>
	<p>language register; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>language register; MINOR</p>	<p>1</p>
	<p>unidiomatic style; MINOR</p>	<p>capitalisation; MINOR</p>	<p>2</p>
	<p>substitution; MINOR</p>	<p>grammar; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>1</p>
	<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>	<p>punctuation; NEUTRAL</p>	<p>1</p>
	<p>grammar; MINOR</p>		
	<p>language register; MINOR</p>		
	<p>language register; NEUTRAL</p>		
	<p>substitution; MINOR</p>		
	<p>grammar; MINOR</p>		
	<p>awkward style; NEUTRAL</p>		
	<p>grammar; MINOR</p>		
	<p>unidiomatic style; MINOR</p>		
	<p>mistranslation; MINOR</p>		
	<p>punctuation; MINOR</p>		
	<p>capitalisation; MINOR</p>		
	<p>grammar; NEUTRAL</p>		
	<p>unidiomatic style; MINOR</p>		
	<p>substitution; MINOR</p>		

	punctuation; NEUTRAL		
	unidiomatic style; MINOR		
	unidiomatic style; MINOR		
	substitution; MINOR		
	capitalisation; MINOR		
	punctuation; MINOR		
	grammar; MINOR		
	grammar; MINOR		
	language register; NEUTRAL		

Appendix 6. TikTok Auto-Translated Captions Error Annotation Data

All Error Annotations	Count	Error Types; Severity	Unique Count	Error Types; Severity	Unique Count	Error Dimension	Dimension Total	Neutral	Minor	Major	Critical	Dimension Total excluding Neutral errors	Percentage of Total excluding Neutral Errors
substitution; MAJOR	2	substitution; MAJOR	10	insertion; MINOR	1	ASR Accuracy	100	8	81	10	1	92	21.96%
unidiomatic style; MINOR	2	unidiomatic style; MINOR	20	deletion; MINOR	7								
grammar; MINOR	5	grammar; MINOR	68	substitution; NEUTRAL	8								
grammar; NEUTRAL	4	grammar; NEUTRAL	51	substitution; MINOR	73								
inconsistent with external reference; NEUTRAL	1	inconsistent with external reference; NEUTRAL	9	substitution; MAJOR	10								
awkward style; NEUTRAL	1	awkward style; NEUTRAL	14	substitution; CRITICAL	1	Terminology	23	1	17	5	0	22	5.25%
substitution; MINOR	6	substitution; MINOR	73	inconsistent with terminology resource; NEUTRAL	1								
punctuation; MINOR	3	punctuation; MINOR	95	inconsistent with terminology resource; MINOR	9								
mistranslation; MINOR	2	mistranslation; MINOR	42	wrong term; MAJOR	5								
substitution; NEUTRAL	2	substitution; NEUTRAL	8	wrong term; MINOR	8								
capitalisation; MINOR	1	capitalisation; MINOR	41	mistranslation; MINOR	42	Accuracy	58	5	48	5	0	53	12.65%
textual conventions; MINOR	1	textual conventions; MINOR	9	mistranslation; MAJOR	2								
punctuation; NEUTRAL	1	punctuation; NEUTRAL	32	overtranslation; NEUTRAL	1								
language register; NEUTRAL	1	language register; NEUTRAL	19	undertranslation; NEUTRAL	2								
addition; NEUTRAL	1	addition; NEUTRAL	1	undertranslation; MINOR	2								
deletion; MINOR	1	deletion; MINOR	7	addition; NEUTRAL	1	Linguistic Conventions	307	91	216	0	0	216	51.55%
grammar; NEUTRAL	3	textual conventions; NEUTRAL	2	omission; NEUTRAL	1								
substitution; MAJOR	1	insertion; MINOR	1	omission; MINOR	4								
textual conventions; NEUTRAL	1	untranslated; MAJOR	1	omission; MAJOR	2								
unidiomatic style; MINOR	2	omission; MINOR	4	untranslated; MAJOR	1								
mistranslation; MINOR	4	mistranslation; MAJOR	2	grammar; NEUTRAL	51	Style	79	43	36	0	0	36	8.59%
punctuation; NEUTRAL	2	omission; MAJOR	2	grammar; MINOR	68								
insertion; MINOR	1	wrong term; MAJOR	5	punctuation; NEUTRAL	32								
substitution; MINOR	1	awkward style; MINOR	10	punctuation; MINOR	95								
untranslated; MAJOR	1	inconsistent with terminology resource; MINOR	9	spelling; NEUTRAL	1								
punctuation; MINOR	5	undertranslation; MINOR	2	spelling; MINOR	3	Total	567	148	398	20	1	419	
omission; MINOR	1	wrong term; MINOR	8	capitalisation; NEUTRAL	5								
mistranslation; MAJOR	1	substitution; CRITICAL	1	capitalisation; MINOR	41								
omission; MAJOR	1	undertranslation; NEUTRAL	2	textual conventions; NEUTRAL	2								
wrong term; MAJOR	1	capitalisation; NEUTRAL	5	textual conventions; MINOR	9								
grammar; MINOR	1	inconsistent with terminology resource; NEUTRAL	1	inconsistent with external reference; NEUTRAL	9	567							
capitalisation; MINOR	2	language register; MINOR	6	language register; NEUTRAL	19								
textual conventions; MINOR	2	spelling; MINOR	3	language register; MINOR	6								
inconsistent with external reference; NEUTRAL	1			awkward style; NEUTRAL	14								
deletion; MINOR	1	spelling; NEUTRAL	1	awkward style; MINOR	10								
substitution; MAJOR	1	unidiomatic style; NEUTRAL	1	unidiomatic style; NEUTRAL	1	94.99%		4.77%	0.24%				
substitution; MINOR	6	overtranslation; NEUTRAL	1	unidiomatic style; MINOR	20								
inconsistent with external reference; NEUTRAL	2	omission; NEUTRAL	1										
awkward style; NEUTRAL	3												
punctuation; MINOR	5												
punctuation; NEUTRAL	9												
grammar; NEUTRAL	2												
grammar; MINOR	2												
capitalisation; MINOR	1												
language register; NEUTRAL	1												
awkward style; MINOR	1												
substitution; NEUTRAL	1												
textual conventions; MINOR	1												
deletion; MINOR	1												
grammar; MINOR	9												
wrong term; MAJOR	3												
grammar; NEUTRAL	1												
substitution; MINOR	8												
mistranslation; MINOR	3												
awkward style; NEUTRAL	2												
punctuation; NEUTRAL	3												
inconsistent with terminology resource; MINOR	1												
capitalisation; MINOR	2												
unidiomatic style; MINOR	1												
punctuation; MINOR	9												
substitution; MAJOR	1												
deletion; MINOR	1												
grammar; NEUTRAL	6												
wrong term; MAJOR	1												
punctuation; NEUTRAL	2												

